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Title: Potential impact of engineered silver nanoparticles in the control of aflatoxins, ochratoxin A and the main aflatoxigenic and ochratoxigenic species affecting foods

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Keywords: Silver nanoparticles; toxigenic *Aspergillus* spp.; fungal growth control; aflatoxins; ochratoxin A, foods.

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Abstract: The potential use of nanotechnology in the control of toxigenic fungi and mycotoxin production has been little explored. In this report, engineered silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) were synthesized and characterized by single particle Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry. Then, their effectiveness in the control of the growth of the main aflatoxigenic and ochratoxigenic species affecting foods and aflatoxins (AFs) and ochratoxin A (OTA) production was studied. The target species and their associated mycotoxins were *Aspergillus flavus* (AFB1 and AFB2), *A. parasiticus* (AFB1, AFB2, AFG1 and AFG2), *A. carbonarius*, *A. niger*, *A. ochraceus*, *A. steynii*, *A. westerdijkiae* and *Penicillium verrucosum* (OTA). Spore suspensions supplemented with AgNPs (average diameter size 30 nm, range 14-100 nm) at doses 0-45 µg/mL were incubated for 2-30 h. At selected exposure times aliquots were removed and cultured on maize-based medium (MBM) for 10 days. In these cultures, percentage of viable spores, effective doses (EDs) to inhibit the number of viable spores to 50%, 90% and 100%, colony lag phases, colony growth rates (GR), EDs to inhibit the colony GR to 50%, 90% and 100% were estimated. AF and OTA levels were determined by UPLC-MS/MS. Under the assayed conditions, effective doses of the AgNPs against all the studied fungal species could be estimated. These doses generally decreased with increasing exposure time and were higher for *A. flavus* and *A. parasiticus* than for ochratoxigenic species. Colonies from spores treated at high exposure times (20-30 h) and variable AgNP doses showed long lag phases or even did not occur depending on the fungal species. Colony GR, as well as AF and OTA levels in MBM cultures decreased when AgNP dose and contact period increased. The factors species, AgNP dose, exposure time and their interactions significantly affect fungal growth and AF and OTA accumulation in MBM. The results suggest that AgNPs only or as active ingredient hosted in paints, films or other polymers could be a good strategy in the management of the main aflatoxigenic and ochratoxigenic species affecting food and AF and OTA contamination.

Highlights

- Extraordinarily effective AgNPs against toxigenic *Aspergillus* spp. were obtained
- Effective doses (ED50, ED90 and ED100) were in the range 2-45 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$
- Antifungal spectra of AgNPs depended on the doses, exposure period and species
- AF and OTA accumulation were closely related to fungal growth rate and lag duration
- AgNPs could have a strong impact on the management of toxigenic fungi and mycotoxins

1 **Potential impact of engineered silver nanoparticles in the control of**
2 **aflatoxins, ochratoxin A and the main aflatoxigenic and ochratoxigenic**
3 **species affecting foods**

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24 **Abstract**

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26 production has been little explored. In this report, engineered silver nanoparticles
27 (AgNPs) were synthesized and characterized by single particle Inductively Coupled
28 Plasma Mass Spectrometry. Then, their effectiveness in the control of the growth of the
29 main aflatoxigenic and ochratoxigenic species affecting foods and aflatoxins (AFs) and
30 ochratoxin A (OTA) production was studied. The target species and their associated
31 mycotoxins were *Aspergillus flavus* (AFB₁ and AFB₂), *A. parasiticus* (AFB₁, AFB₂, AFG₁
32 and AFG₂), *A. carbonarius*, *A. niger*, *A. ochraceus*, *A. steynii*, *A. westerdijkiae* and
33 *Penicillium verrucosum* (OTA). Spore suspensions supplemented with AgNPs (average
34 diameter size 30 nm, range 14-100 nm) at doses 0–45 µg/mL were incubated for 2–30
35 h. At selected exposure times aliquots were removed and cultured on maize-based
36 medium (MBM) for 10 days. In these cultures, percentage of viable spores, effective
37 doses (EDs) to inhibit the number of viable spores to 50%, 90% and 100%, colony lag
38 phases, colony growth rates (GR), EDs to inhibit the colony GR to 50%, 90% and
39 100% were estimated. AF and OTA levels were determined by UPLC-MS/MS. Under
40 the assayed conditions, effective doses of the AgNPs against all the studied fungal
41 species could be estimated. These doses generally decreased with increasing
42 exposure time and were higher for *A. flavus* and *A. parasiticus* than for ochratoxigenic
43 species. Colonies from spores treated at high exposure times (20–30 h) and variable
44 AgNP doses showed long lag phases or even did not occur depending on the fungal
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46 AgNP dose and contact period increased. The factors species, AgNP dose, exposure
47 time and their interactions significantly affect fungal growth and AF and OTA
48 accumulation in MBM. The results suggest that AgNPs only or as active ingredient
49 hosted in paints, films or other polymers could be a good strategy in the management
50 of the main aflatoxigenic and ochratoxigenic species affecting food and AF and OTA
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54

55 1. Introduction

56 The most important and frequent mycotoxins in foods and feeds are aflatoxins
57 (AFs) and ochratoxin A (OTA) (European Union, 2017). These fungal secondary
58 metabolites have strong detrimental impact on public health and economy (Bui-Klimke
59 & Wu, 2015; IARC, 1993; Klingelhöfer, Zhu, Braun, Bendels, Brüggmann, &
60 Groneberg, 2018; Kumar, Mahato, Kamle, Mohanta, & Kang, 2017). In general, AFs and
61 OTA have been widely reported in cereals and cereal-based products. AFs are mainly
62 found in maize (Battilani et al., 2012; James & Zikankuba, 2018; Pereira, Fernandes &
63 Cunha, 2014) and other food such as nuts, cocoa, dried fruits (Taniwaki, Pitt, & Magan,
64 2018) or milk (Iqbal, Jinap, Pirouz, & Faizal, 2015). OTA is mainly found in small grain
65 cereals (Duarte, Pena, & Lino, 2010), beer, wine (Mateo, Medina, Mateo, & Jiménez,
66 2007), grapes (Covarelli, Beccari, Marini, & Tosi, 2012) or coffee (Taniwaki et al.,
67 2018), among others. Co-occurrence of AFs and OTA in cereals and nuts is usual.
68 Currently these mycotoxins are regulated in the foodstuffs of highest risk (European
69 Commission, 2006 and subsequent amendments).

70 The most frequent toxigenic species related with the occurrence of AFs in foods
71 and feeds are *Aspergillus flavus* and *A. parasiticus*, from section *Flavi* (Giorni, Bertuzzi,
72 & Battilani, 2016; Taniwaki et al., 2018). The main ochratoxigenic species are *A.*
73 *carbonarius*, *A. niger* from section *Nigri*, *A. ochraceus*, *A. steynii* and *A. westerdijkiae*
74 from section *Circumdati* (Gil-Serna, García-Díaz, González-Jaén, Vázquez, & Patiño,
75 2018; Medina, Mateo, López-Ocaña, Valle-Algarra, & Jiménez, 2005) and *Penicillium*
76 *verrucosum* from section *Viridicata* (Lunch & Frisvad, 2003).

77 For a long time, prevention and control of these toxigenic fungi and mycotoxins
78 in agricultural commodities have been priority objectives in food security and food
79 safety. To achieve these challenges, good agricultural and storage practices (Torres,
80 Barros, Palacios, Chulze, & Battilani, 2014), environmental factors, especially
81 associated to climate change (Battilani et al., 2012; Battilani, 2016; Marroquín-

82 Cardona, Johnson, Phillips, & Hayes, 2014) or chemical and natural antifungal agents
83 affecting fungal growth and mycotoxin production (Gómez, Tarazona, Mateo-Castro,
84 Gimeno-Adelantado, Jiménez, & Mateo, 2018; Mateo, Gómez, Gimeno-Adelantado,
85 Romera, Mateo-Castro, & Jiménez, 2017a; Medina, Jiménez, Mateo, & Magan, 2007)
86 have been studied in the last years. However, the problems associated with
87 aflatoxigenic and ochratoxigenic fungi and AFs and OTA accumulation in cereals and
88 other foods (European Union, 2017) require new approaches (Mateo et al., 2017b;
89 Nguyen, Long, Joly, & Dantigny, 2017; Tarazona et al., 2018). Moreover, it has been
90 found that sub-inhibitory doses of chemical antifungal agents can result in an increase
91 of mycotoxin production (Mateo, Valle-Algarra, Jiménez, & Magan, 2013; Mateo, Valle-
92 Algarra, Mateo-Castro, & Jiménez, 2011a; Medina et al., 2007) and in development of
93 resistances (Ma & Michailides, 2005). Hence, new strategies and identification of new
94 fungal molecular targets become significant steps towards food protection.

95 Nanotechnology is not new, particularly nanoparticles have immense
96 applications in agriculture, nutrition, medicine, health and other sciences (Baker,
97 Volova, Prudnikova, Satish, & Prasad, 2017; Hofmann-Antenbrink, Grainger, &
98 Hofmann, 2015; McClements, 2017; Rai et al., 2018). Among nanoparticles, silver
99 nanoparticles (AgNPs) deserve special attention. The antimicrobial action of AgNPs
100 has been reported on pathogenic bacteria (Ahmad et al., 2017; da Silva-Ferreira,
101 ConzFerreira, Lima, Frases, de Souza, & Sant'Anna, 2017), fungi (Jogee, Ingle, &
102 Mahendra, 2017; Kim, Jung, Lamsal, Kim, Min, & Lee, 2012) and viruses (Huy, Hien,
103 Thanh, Thuy, Chung, & Hung, 2017). However, the antifungal activity of AgNPs on
104 toxigenic fungi affecting crops in pre- and postharvest and their effect on mycotoxin
105 biosynthesis have been very little explored (Abd-Elsalam, Hashim, Alghuthaymi, &
106 Said-Galiev, 2017). In addition to its antimicrobial action, some important advantages
107 of silver-based antimicrobials are their excellent thermal stability and their health and
108 environmental safety (Kumar et al., 2017).

109 The aims of the present study were: i) to evaluate the potential of AgNPs as
110 antifungal agent against the main aflatoxigenic (*A. flavus* and *A. parasiticus*) and
111 ochratoxigenic (*A. carbonarius*, *A. niger*, *A. ochraceus*, *A. steynii*, *A. westerdijkiae* and
112 *Penicillium verrucosum*) species affecting crops, and ii) to evaluate the effect of AgNPs
113 on AFB₁, AFB₂, AFG₁, AFG₂ and OTA production by the fungal species included in the
114 study.

115 **2. Materials and Methods**

116 *2.1. Reagents and standards*

117 Silver nitrate (>99.9% pure) and standards of AFB₁, AFB₂, AFG₁, AFG₂ and
118 OTA were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Alcobendas, Spain). Yeast extract, and
119 sodium acetate were purchased from Panreac (Montcada i Reixac, Barcelona, Spain).
120 Sodium borohydride (NaBH₄, >99% pure), trisodium citrate (99% pure), sodium
121 hydroxide, ammonium formate and Tween 80 were from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany).
122 All reagents supplied were of analytical grade. Acetonitrile, chloroform, formic acid,
123 methanol and ethanol (all LC grade) were from J.T. Baker (Deventer, the Netherlands).
124 Pure water was obtained from a Milli-Q Plus apparatus (Millipore, Billerica, MA, USA).

125 *2.2. Preparation of AgNPs*

126 AgNPs were obtained using basically the procedure described by Agnihotri,
127 Mukherji, and Mukherji (2014) for synthesis of NP with an average diameter of 30 nm.
128 NaBH₄ as a primary reductant and trisodium citrate, both as secondary reductant and
129 stabilizing agent were employed. A volume of 180 mL of 0.001M NaBH₄ and 0.0055 M
130 trisodium citrate was heated at 60 °C for 30 min in the dark under vigorous stirring.
131 Then, 20 mL of a 0.004 M solution of AgNO₃ was added drop wise. The temperature
132 was raised to 90 °C and the pH was set to 10.5 with 0.1 M solution of NaOH. After 20
133 min heating at 90 °C under continuous stirring, the mixture was let to cool at room

134 temperature. Then, the AgNP suspension was centrifuged at 14000 g at 4 °C for 20
135 min. The supernatant was carefully withdrawn and discarded, and the AgNPs were
136 washed with pure water and centrifuged under the same conditions six times. Finally,
137 the residue was suspended in pure water and stored at 4 °C. The pH was 6.6 ± 0.1 .
138 After the repeated washing/centrifugation steps most unexpended reactants and
139 products others than citrate-capped AgNP (H_2 produced by oxidation or hydrolysis of
140 BH_4^- , boric acid, nitrate, excess citrate), were removed from the suspension. Moreover,
141 Ag^+ concentration was not detectable (lack of turbidity) by mixing the supernatant liquid
142 with 5.12 M aqueous solution of NaCl in a 4:1 v/v ratio. Thus, no products at levels that
143 may be toxic to fungal spores different from the AgNPs are expected in the final
144 suspension.

145 *2.3. AgNP characterization by single particle inductively coupled plasma mass* 146 *spectrometry (SP-ICP-MS)*

147 Characterization of the AgNP suspension was performed using SP-ICP-MS.
148 The reagents were a high purity certified standard of Ag of 1000 mg/L (Charleston, SC,
149 USA) and a standard of Au nanoparticles of 50 nm size and 3.51×10^{10} AuNPs/mL
150 (Sigma-Aldrich). A standard of 1 mg Ag/L was prepared by dilution of the certified
151 standard and standards of AuNPs (50 nm) were also prepared by successive dilution of
152 the concentrate standard. The original standard and the successive dilutions were
153 sonicated for 10 min. The samples were prepared as described for AuNP standards.
154 The conditions and parameters for ICP-MS analysis were:

155 Instrument: ICP-MS Agilent model 7900, with concentric nebulizer type
156 Micromist, a Scott-type spray camera, Pt-cone interphase, double lens off-axis,
157 hyperbolic quadrupole as mass filter and octopole collision/reaction cell using He and
158 H_2 , respectively. Plasma gas flow rate (15 L/min); auxiliary gas flow (1.0 L/min); RF
159 Power (1550 W); RF Matching (1.80 V); sampling depth (8.0 mm); nebulizer pump (0.1
160 rps); carrier gas (1.07 L/min); sample uptake rate (mL/min) 0.35; plasma mode: low

161 matrix; Spray chamber temperature (°C) 2.0. Integration parameters: Acquisition mode:
162 TRA (Time Resolved Analysis Mode); Integration time/mass (0.0030 s); Acquisition
163 time (60 s). Cell parameters: Isotope monitored ¹⁰⁷Ag; Cell gas He; Cell gas flow (4.0
164 mL/min); Energy discrimination (2.0 V); Octopole RF (200 V).

165 *2.4. AgNP characterization by Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM)*

166 The suspension of AgNPs was examined by TEM to obtain the distribution of
167 nanoparticle sizes by a complementary method. A JEOL JEM-1010 (JEOL Co., Ltd.,
168 Tokyo, Japan) electron microscope of accelerating voltage from 40 kV to 100 kV with
169 digital camera AMT RX80 (8 Mpx) was used. A drop of the AgNP suspension in pure
170 water was deposited onto a Formvar/carbon film 300-mesh copper grid and, after
171 complete solvent evaporation, the grid was inserted in the instrument sampler.

172 *2.5. Fungal strains and inoculum preparation*

173 Isolates of the target species and strains *A. flavus* (Af22c), *A. parasiticus*
174 (Ap31c), *A. carbonarius* (Ac1102g), *A. niger* (An27g), *A. ochraceus* (Ao37c), *A.*
175 *westerdijkiae* (Aw29c) and *A. steynii* (As11c) were previously isolated from cereals and
176 grapes grown in Spain. The strain of *Penicillium verrucosum* (ref. Pv12 in our
177 collection) was kindly provided by Prof. Rolf Geisen (Max Rubner Institute, Federal
178 Research Institute of Nutrition and Food, Karlsruhe, Germany). Identification of fungi
179 was carried out by conventional and PCR protocols (Medina et al., 2005; Mateo, Gil-
180 Serna, Patiño, & Jiménez, 2011b). All strains are held in the Mycology and Mycotoxins
181 Group Culture Collection (Valencia University, Spain). Before carrying out the study,
182 the strains were grown in Yeast Extract Sucrose agar medium (20 g agar, 20 g yeast
183 extract, 150 g sucrose, 1 g MgSO₄·7H₂O, 1000 mL water). The medium was
184 autoclaved at 115 °C for 30 min and poured into Petri dishes. The strains were
185 inoculated on the center of the plates and incubated at 28 °C for 7 days. *P. verrucosum*
186 cultures were incubated at 20 °C. Spores of these fresh cultures were used to prepare

187 inocula for further experiments on AgNP efficacy to control fungal growth and
188 mycotoxin production.

189 *2.6. Impact of AgNPs on the growth of toxigenic fungi*

190 *2.6.1. Preparation of culture medium*

191 Maize-based medium (MBM) (3% w/v of milled maize grains + 2% w/v agar in
192 pure water), a representative matrix based on cereal was used to investigate the effect
193 of AgNPs on fungal growth. Maize grains were previously analyzed to ensure they had
194 undetectable levels of AFs and OTA. MBM was placed in Erlenmeyer flasks and
195 autoclaved at 115 °C for 30 min. Water activity (a_w) level in the sterile medium was
196 measured in a flask control and adjusted in all flasks to 0.99 by addition of sterile
197 glycerol/water using a moisture adsorption curve for MBM previously determined. A
198 RTD-502 unit (Novasina GmbH, Pfäffikon, Switzerland) was used to perform all a_w
199 measurements. Then, the medium was poured into Petri dishes (25 mL/dish).

200 *2.6.2. Treatments*

201 Treatments were performed once the AgNP concentration of the suspension
202 was determined. Contact assays (fungal spores-AgNPs) under different AgNP doses
203 and exposure times were carried out. To this purpose, tubes were added with aliquots
204 of the AgNP stock suspension necessary to contain 0 (control), 2, 5, 10, 15, 30 and 45
205 μg of AgNPs/mL in a final volume of 5 mL. The remaining volume up to 5 mL was
206 completed with sterile pure water and a sterile solution of Tween 80 to have a
207 concentration of the surfactant of 0.005%. These controls and AgNP suspensions were
208 inoculated with 1×10^5 spores/mL of fresh fungal cultures (7 days old) and vortexed for
209 30 s by a Stuart vortex mixer to facilitate a uniform and optimal homogenization.
210 Controls and treatments were placed in an orbital shaker (Infors-HT Aerotron,
211 Bottminghen, Switzerland) at 60 rpm and 25 °C for 30 h. The non-polar surfactant
212 Tween 80 is useful to maintain both spores and AgNPs in suspension while shaking

213 assure homogeneity of the medium during treatments. Tween 80 helps stabilize AgNP
214 suspensions preventing their aggregation (Kvítek, Panáček, Soukupová, Kolář,
215 Večeřová, Prucek, et al., 2008). Moreover, to check the stability of the suspension
216 during the exposure period of the spores to AgNPs the spectrum of the diluted
217 suspensions in water containing Tween 80 (0.005%) was recorded from 300 to 800 nm
218 over time up to 30 h in 10-mm quartz cell using an Agilent 8453 diode array
219 spectrophotometer. The presence of Ag⁺ in the medium along the exposure time was
220 tested in the supernatant liquid of centrifuged tubes as previously described for the
221 AgNP initial stock suspension (Section 2.2).

222 2.6.3. Evaluation of individual spore viability after treatments

223 To evaluate the number of viable spores of the different fungal species in
224 control and treatments, an aliquot of 500 µL from test tubes (Section 2.6.2) was
225 removed at 0, 2, 4, 20 and 30 h of contact (fungal spores-AgNPs) and transferred to
226 tubes containing 4.5 mL of sterile saline solution (9 g NaCl/L pure water). The 10⁻¹
227 dilution of the sample was vortexed for 30 s and used to prepare successive tenfold
228 serial dilutions (10⁻²–10⁻⁵) in sterile saline solution. A volume of 100 µL of each dilution
229 was spread on the surface of Petri dishes containing MBM. To facilitate the growth of
230 each species, the inoculated plates were incubated at 28 °C, except *A. flavus* and *A.*
231 *parasiticus* cultures, which were incubated at 37 °C (Gómez et al., 2018), and *P.*
232 *verrucosum*, which was incubated at 20 °C (Lunch & Frisvad, 2003). Cultures were
233 incubated in the dark for 5 days, enclosed in sealed plastic containers together with
234 beakers of a glycerol–water solution matching the same a_w (0.99) to maintain a
235 constant equilibrium relative humidity inside the boxes. After the incubation period,
236 fungal colony forming units/mL (CFU/mL), effective doses to reduce the number of
237 viable spores to 50% (ED₅₀), 90% (ED₉₀), and 100 % (ED₁₀₀) with respect to untreated
238 controls were estimated by graphical interpolation in the plots of CFU/mL vs AgNP

239 dose at each exposure time. All experiments were performed in triplicate and repeated
240 twice.

241 2.6.4. Evaluation of colony growth after treatments

242 For monitoring colony growth, a 3- μ L aliquot of spore suspensions (control and
243 treatments) (Section 2.6.2) was removed at 2, 4, 20, and 30 h of contact (fungal
244 spores-AgNPs) and centrally inoculated on the surface of MBM Petri plates, which
245 were incubated at 28 °C, except *A. flavus* and *A. parasiticus* (37 °C), and *P.*
246 *verrucosum* (20 °C). Cultures were incubated in the dark for 10 days, enclosed in
247 sealed plastic containers together with beakers of a glycerol–water solution matching
248 the same a_w (0.99). The effect of treatments (AgNP concentration and exposure time)
249 on colony lag period and colony radial growth rate (GR) of the different species was
250 determined in these cultures. Lag phase was considered as the time (days) to reach a
251 colony 5 mm diameter. Then, two perpendicular colony diameters were measured
252 every day and the mean radius was calculated. GR (mm/day) of the colony was
253 calculated in all cultures as the slope of the line obtained by linear regression of mean
254 radius vs time. The AgNP doses (μ g/mL) necessary for 50%, 90% and 100% growth
255 inhibition (ED_{50} , ED_{90} and ED_{100}) in MBM were estimated, when possible, from the plots
256 of GR vs AgNP dose in treatments. All experiments were performed in triplicate and
257 repeated twice.

258 2.7. Impact of AgNPs on mycotoxin accumulation

259 To determine the effect of AgNPs on mycotoxin production, at the end of
260 incubation period (10 days), the cultures in MBM used for GR evaluation were removed
261 from Petri dishes and analyzed for AFs and OTA. Previously, calibration and recovery
262 assays were carried out. The methodology described by Romera, Mateo, Mateo-
263 Castro, Gómez, Gimeno-Adelantado, and Jiménez (2018) was followed with some

264 modifications related to matrix nature, calibration, recovery studies and type and levels
265 of mycotoxins (as described in Sections 2.7.1, 2.7.2 and 2.7.3).

266 2.7.1. Calibration

267 Matrix-matched calibration was performed to overcome the matrix effect.
268 Mycotoxin standard solutions were obtained by dissolution of pure standards of AFs in
269 chloroform or the standard of OTA in ethanol and further dilution in acetonitrile/water
270 formic acid (80:19:1, v/v/v). AF and OTA calibration standards were prepared by
271 addition of variable volumes of AFB₁, AFB₂, AFG₁, AFG₂ or OTA standard solutions (2–
272 1000 ng/mL) to extracts of blank (non-inoculated) MBM. These extracts were obtained
273 by mixing two g of MBM with 8 mL of acetonitrile/water/formic acid (80:19:1, v/v/v) and
274 shaking in orbital shaker (Infors-HT Aerotron, Bottmingen, Switzerland) for 1 h. After
275 centrifugation (4260 g, 5 min), two mL of the supernatant was evaporated to dryness
276 under a stream of N₂, added with the appropriate volume of mycotoxin standards and
277 diluted with acetonitrile/water/formic acid (80:19:1, v/v/v) to provide the desired
278 concentration. Standards were filtered using a syringe filter (0.22 µm, PTFE) and
279 injected into the UPLC-MS/MS system. Calibration lines were obtained by linear
280 regression (weighting by 1/x) of the areas of peaks associated to quantifier ion of each
281 analyte vs mycotoxin concentration.

282 2.7.2. Recovery studies

283 For determination of mycotoxin levels in MBM cultures, the method was initially
284 validated by analysis of blank MBM spiked with AFs and OTA (n = 5) at various levels.
285 They were performed by adding variable volumes of AFB₁, AFB₂, AFG₁ and AFG₂ or
286 OTA standard solutions to Erlenmeyer flasks containing 25 g of autoclaved MBM and
287 cooled to approx. 45 °C. The concentration range for recovery studies was 5–300 ng/g.
288 After homogenization, the medium was poured in Petri dishes and let to cool at room
289 temperature. Then, the total of solid medium (approx. 25 g) was cut into small pieces
290 and homogenized in a stomacher. About two g of the spiked homogenate was placed

291 into a Falcon tube for mycotoxin determination. Mycotoxins were extracted by adding 8
292 mL acetonitrile/water/formic acid (80:19:1, v/v/v). Falcon tubes were capped and
293 shaken in orbital shaker for 1 h. After centrifugation (4260 g, 5 min), two mL of the
294 supernatant was filtered through 0.22- μ m PTFE syringe filter prior to be injected into
295 the UPLC-MS/MS system.

296 2.7.3. Mycotoxin determination in maize-based cultures

297 At the end of the incubation period, AFs in cultures of *A. flavus* and *A.*
298 *parasiticus*, used for GR evaluation, and OTA in the cultures of the ochratoxigenic
299 aspergilli and *P. verrucosum* were determined. To this purpose, regardless of colony
300 diameter, the whole culture (substrate plus fungal biomass) was cut into small pieces,
301 removed from Petri dishes, weighed, homogenized in a stomacher, and analyzed for
302 AFs or OTA. Extraction, centrifugation and filtration were performed as described in
303 Section 2.7.2. Filtered extracts were injected into the UPLC–MS/MS system. When
304 mycotoxin levels were too high for the linear calibration range, the extracts were
305 appropriately diluted with the same solvent before injection.

306 2.8. UPLC-MS/MS conditions

307 The separation and MS/MS conditions were reported by Romera et al. (2018).
308 Briefly, the UPLC–MS/MS system consisted of an ACQUITY UPLC™ system (Waters,
309 Manchester, UK), provided with an electrospray ionization interface (ESI). Separation
310 was performed at 25 °C in an ACQUITY UPLC BEH C18 column (50 × 2.1 mm, 1.7 μ m
311 particle size) (Waters). The injection volume was 30 μ L. The mobile phase was a time-
312 programmed combination of water containing ammonium formate (0.15 mmol/L) and
313 formic acid (0.1%) and methanol at a flow-rate of 0.35 mL/min. MS/MS detection was
314 performed by an ACQUITY TQD tandem quadrupole mass spectrometer (Waters Co.,
315 Milford, MA, USA). The ESI interface was used in positive ion mode (ESI+).

316 2.9. Statistics

317 Data were analyzed by multifactor analysis of variance (ANOVA) and linear
318 regression using Statgraphics Centurion XV.II statistical package (StatPoint, Inc., VA,
319 USA). *Post-hoc* Duncan's multiple range test ($\alpha = 0.05$) was used to find homogenous
320 groups when significant differences between factors were revealed by ANOVA. For
321 calculation purposes, undetectable levels were assumed to be zero.

322 **3. Results and Discussion**

323 *3.1. Characterization of AgNPs*

324 Fig. 1 shows the distribution of AgNP diameters obtained by SP-ICP-MS. The
325 average size of AgNPs was 30 nm (range 20– >100 nm), the number of particles/mL
326 was 6.48×10^{10} and the Ag concentration 59.24 mg/L. The minimum particle diameter
327 to be detected due to the background of the AgNP diluted suspension (1500 cps with a
328 dwell time of 3 ms) was 20 nm. The concentration of AgNPs obtained by this method
329 was lower than the concentration reported by Agnihotri et al. (2014) for 30 nm size
330 AgNPs (1.71×10^{13} NP/mL). It can be due to possible differences in experimental
331 conditions during the synthesis, such as speed of stirring, heating or AgNO₃ addition,
332 centrifugation force and the different method used for particle measurement (dynamic
333 light scattering or SP-ICP-MS).

334 Fig. 2(a) shows a micrograph obtained by TEM where it can be seen that most
335 nanoparticles are approximately spherical and have between 20 and 40 nm average
336 diameter. The size distribution by TEM is observed in Fig. 2(b). The diameter range
337 was 14-100 nm, and agrees with Fig. 1 although diameters between 14 and 20 nm
338 were observed. The average diameter was 30.9 nm. Diameters > 100 nm detected by
339 SP-ICP-MS might be due to agglomerates of small-size AgNPs.

340 *3.2. Effect of AgNPs on individual spore viability*

341 Little is known regarding the effects of AgNPs on phytopathogenic and toxigenic
342 fungi, because most studies have been focused on bacterial and viral pathogens for
343 human and animals. Here, we evaluated the antifungal activity of AgNPs against the
344 main toxigenic *Aspergillus* spp. affecting crops and their effect on the biosynthesis of
345 the major mycotoxins associated with these species in foods and feeds.

346 Fig. 4 and Table 1 show the effect of AgNP dose and exposure time (AgNPs-
347 fungal spores) on the individual spore viability for the studied fungal species. The
348 number of viable spores in control and treatments (CFU/mL) was estimated in MBM
349 cultures. According to ANOVA, the factors AgNP dose, exposure time and fungal
350 species and the three possible two-way interactions between factors significantly
351 influenced spore viability. Overall, when the dose and/or exposure time increased the
352 number of viable spores decreased. A dose of 15 μg AgNPs/mL applied during 20 h
353 killed 100% of spores of all the ochratoxigenic species tested. The influence of the
354 species, although significant, was not so clear. Spores from *A. flavus* and *A. parasiticus*
355 were the most resistant while those from *A. steynii* and *A. westerdijkiae* appeared to be
356 the most susceptible. The Duncan's test ($\alpha = 0.05$) found seven, three and four
357 homogenous groups for the factors AgNP dose, exposure time and fungal species,
358 respectively (Table 2).

359 The effective doses of AgNPs to reduce the number of viable spores to 50%,
360 90% and 100% (ED_{50} , ED_{90} and ED_{100}) in treatments respect to untreated controls
361 appear in Table 1. Under the assayed conditions, exposure of spores to AgNPs for 2 h
362 permitted to estimate these three parameters only in *P. verrucosum* treatments. At 4 h
363 exposure time the ED_{50} was estimated for all the species (except in *A. parasiticus*
364 treatments) and the ED_{90} and ED_{100} only in *A. carbonarius* and *P. verrucosum*
365 treatments. At 20 and 30 h exposure time, the three parameters could be estimated for
366 all the species. Thus, at 20 h exposure time, the ED_{50} , ED_{90} and ED_{100} ranges for all the
367 species were 1.5–7.3, 6.8–17.7, and 10–45 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, respectively, while at 30 h, the
368 respective ranges were 1.1–3.2, 1.8–14.5, and 5–30 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ (Table 1). Spores of *A.*

369 *parasiticus* and *A. flavus* followed by spores of *P. verrucosum* were the less
370 susceptible to AgNPs, which agrees with the inclusion of these species in the same
371 homogenous group by Duncan's test (Table 2).

372 The stability of the AgNPs over time in the liquid medium used for spore
373 exposure (water plus 0.005% Tween 80) was assessed by UV-visible
374 spectrophotometry (Fig. 3). The bulk suspension was diluted with Tween 80 giving a
375 greenish-yellow suspension. The typical surface plasmon absorption peak was
376 observed and the maximum occurred at 405–409 nm and remained practically
377 unchanged for at least 30 hours. No shoulder around 350 nm that may be attributable
378 to bulk silver and no AgNP deposit at the cell bottom was observed. The wavelengths
379 at what the maximum appears correspond well with the values reported for citrate-
380 coated AgNPs with diameters around 30 nm by Paramelle, Sadovoy, Gorelik, Free,
381 Hoble and Fernig (2014). This behavior supports lack of agglomeration and agrees
382 with preservation of the nanodimensional character of the AgNPs in presence of Tween
383 80, which acts as reductant and stabilizer (Kvítek et al. 2008; Li, Zhang, Hu, Sui, Qian
384 & Chen, 2012). As citrate acts a stabilizing agent of AgNP during the synthesis,
385 addition of Tween 80 during the exposure phase of fungal spores provides additional
386 stabilization. Presence of ionic silver in treatments along the time of contact AgNP-
387 spores was not detectable using the same test applied to bulk AgNP suspension.

388 3.3. Effect of AgNPs on colony growth

389 Fig. 5 shows the lag phases of fungal colonies growing in MBM inoculated with
390 spore populations from controls and treatments. For statistical treatment, when growth
391 was not observed during the incubation time (10 days), a lag-value of 10 days was
392 arbitrarily considered. Average lag phases ranged between 0.8 (control of *A.*
393 *carbonarius*) and >10 days depending on the species and the treatment. Lack of
394 growth or very long lag phases were observed in cultures inoculated with spores
395 previously exposed for 30 h to AgNPs doses > 5 µg/mL, regardless of the fungal

396 species. The longest measurable lag phase at 30 h contact time was 6.6 days in
397 cultures of *P. verrucosum* inoculated with spores treated with 10 µg AgNPs/mL.

398 ANOVA shows that the factors fungal species, AgNP dose, exposure time and
399 the interactions species × exposure time and AgNP dose × exposure time significantly
400 influenced ($p < 0.05$) the lag phase duration. The Duncan's test grouped the six doses
401 in six homogeneous groups and the species in two homogeneous groups, one formed
402 by *A. flavus*, *A. parasiticus* and *A. niger* and another one, formed by the remaining
403 species (Table 2). Regarding the exposure time, the test grouped 2 and 4 h together
404 while 20 and 30 h formed one group each. The lag phase in cultures was negatively
405 correlated with the number of viable spores in treatments ($R = - 0.785$). This is logical
406 because of the negative relationship of spore viability with exposure time and AgNP
407 dose.

408 After the lag period, the colony GR of the different species in MBM inoculated
409 with treated and non-treated spores was plotted vs AgNP dose (Fig. 6). ANOVA
410 showed that the factors AgNP dose, exposure time and fungal species, and their
411 mutual two-way interactions significantly influenced colony GR ($p < 0.01$). Four
412 homogenous groups were depicted by Duncan's test for each single factor (Table 2).

413 The effective doses of AgNPs to reduce the GR of the colonies growing in MBM
414 to 50%, 90% and 100% (ED_{50} , ED_{90} and ED_{100}) respect to the GR of controls under the
415 assayed conditions appear in Table 3. At 2 h exposure of spores to AgNPs, these
416 doses could be estimated only for *P. verrucosum*. At 4 h exposure, they could be
417 estimated for *P. verrucosum* and *A. carbonarius* while at 20–30 h exposure these
418 parameters could be estimated for all the assayed species. The lowest ED_{100} (5.0
419 µg/mL) was estimated at 30 h exposure for *A. ochraceus*, *A. steynii* and *A.*
420 *westerdijkiae*. This is in agreement with the high susceptibility to AgNPs of the
421 respective spores (Table 1).

422 A critical comparative analysis of our results with those found by other authors
423 is very difficult due to the scarcity of studies related to the impact of AgNPs on

424 toxigenic fungi (spore viability, colony growth rate or effective doses ED₅₀, ED₉₀ and
425 ED₁₀₀). Moreover, the methodology used by the different authors is dissimilar and
426 significant factors related to fungal growth, such as a_w in the medium, have not been
427 controlled. Most of the studies have been carried out incorporating the nanoparticles
428 into the culture medium. Therefore, the effects of exposure time and their interaction
429 with possible effective doses, in order to optimize and minimize the levels of AgNPs in
430 the medium, have not been studied.

431 Among toxigenic *Aspergillus* spp affecting crops, some authors have reported
432 the effect of different types of AgNPs on species from section *Flavi*. Thus, Yassin et al.
433 (2017) studied the effect of AgNPs on *A. flavus* var. *columnaris* in potato dextrose agar
434 (PDA) medium supplemented with AgNPs (size 3–13 nm). Cultures were incubated at
435 28 °C for 10 days and colony diameters were measured daily. The ED₅₀ and ED₉₅ were
436 224.5 ppm and 4001.8 ppm, respectively. Al-Othman, Abd El-aziz, Mahmoud, Eifan, El-
437 shikh, and Majrashi (2014) assayed the effectivity of AgNPs (size 5–30 nm) on different
438 strains of *A. flavus* by the same method at 25 °C. Colony inhibition rate averaged 86.3
439 % at a AgNP dose of 150 ppm and 8.9 % at a dose of 50 ppm. Egger, Lehmann,
440 Height, Loessner and Schuppler (2009) observed that development of visible colonies
441 of *A. niger* on agar malt extract plates was completely inhibited by silver
442 nanocomposite (1 and 10 nm) at doses of 2000 µg/mL. Ismaiel and Tharwat (2014),
443 using agar well diffusion assays on yeast sucrose agar, found a MIC value of AgNPs of
444 70 µg/mL against *A. flavus* and a minimal lethal concentration of 120 µg/mL. Mousavi
445 and Pourtalebi (2015) in potato dextrose broth medium reported a MIC value of 180 µg
446 AgNP/mL against *A. parasiticus*.

447 All the effective antifungal AgNPs levels cited above against *A. flavus*, *A.*
448 *parasiticus* or *A. niger* are higher than those found in our study for these species and
449 for the remaining fungal species studied. However, it should be noted that, in our study,
450 contact assays of fungal spores with AgNPs was carried out in liquid medium and then
451 treated spores were transferred to MBM free of AgNPs. In these last cultures, the effect

452 of the previous treatment was evaluated. Bocate et al. (2019), using broth microdilution
453 assays incubated at 30 °C for 48 h, found AgNPs CMI values of 8, 4, 8, 4, 8 (µg/mL) for
454 *A. flavus*, *A. melleus*, *A. nomius*, *A. ochraceus* and *A. parasiticus*, respectively, and
455 minimal fungicidal concentrations (MFC) of 64, 16, 32, 16 and 32 µg/mL, respectively.
456 These results, with slight variations, are in agreement with those obtained in our study.
457 Qian et al. (2013) reported a CMI of the AgNPs against *A. flavus* of 0.5 µg/mL using a
458 microdilution method and incubation for 48 h at 25 °C. Kotzybik, Gräf, Kugler, Stoll,
459 Greiner, Geisen, et al. (2016) studied the effect of AgNPs (0.65-200 nm) on the growth
460 of *P. verrucosum* and production of OTA and citrinin in malt extract liquid medium. After
461 7 incubation days at 25 °C they found that AgNPs with a nominal size of 0.65 nm inhibit
462 the germination of *P. verrucosum* at concentrations > 2 ppm, AgNPs with 5-nm size
463 inhibit fungal growth at concentrations > 5 ppm and larger particles (50 nm, 200 nm)
464 lead only to a weak inhibition over the whole concentration range assayed. Mycotoxin
465 production was associated to fungal growth level. However, the mold was only
466 marginally affected by AgNPs treatments applied after the fungus had already grown 7
467 days at 25°C. In our study, the germination of *P. verrucosum* spores was totally
468 inhibited by AgNPs with an average diameter of 30 nm at doses of 45 µg/mL for 2-4 h
469 and at doses 15 µg/mL for 20-30 h.

470 Although little is known about the particular effects of nanoparticles on toxigenic
471 fungi, according to Al-Othman et al. (2014), AgNPs affect cell functions and cause
472 deformation in fungal hyphae of *A. flavus*, as well as malformation, hypertrophy and
473 spore number reduction. Kotzybik et al. (2016) reported that small-sized AgNPs (≤ 5
474 nm) easily penetrate into the mycelial filaments of *P. verrucosum* producing silver
475 agglomerates localized within the cytoplasm whereas larger particles (50–100) nm did
476 not. Thus, they suggest that the AgNP effectivity to inhibit fungal growth and mycotoxin
477 biosynthesis depends strongly on the size and the concentration of the nanoparticles.
478 In addition, considering the results of our study, the intensity of those AgNP effects on

479 fungal structure and cell functions, could be also dependent on the fungal species but
480 future research is necessary to confirm this hypothesis.

481 3.4. Mycotoxin determination

482 3.4.1. Validation of the UPLC-MS/MS method

483 For AFs, mean recoveries were 85% (AFB₁), 88% (AFB₂), 77 % (AFG₁), and
484 90% (AFG₂). The limits of detection (LOD) (ng/g MBM) based on a signal-to-noise ratio
485 of 3:1 were 0.15 for AFB₁, 0.2 for AFB₂, 0.2 for AFG₁ and 0.3 for AFG₂. For OTA, mean
486 recovery obtained from spiking experiments was 86% and the LOD based on a signal-
487 to-noise ratio of 3:1 was 0.2 ng/g MBM. Limits of quantification (LOQ) were set at 3.3 x
488 LOD. Relative standard deviations in recovery experiments ranged 5–9% for AFs and
489 OTA.

490 3.4.2. Effect of AgNPs on mycotoxin production

491 The MBM cultures used for growth studies were also used for monitoring
492 mycotoxin production by aflatoxigenic and ochratoxigenic species at the end of the
493 incubation period. Fig. 7 shows the mean AF levels in cultures of *A. flavus* and *A.*
494 *parasiticus*. ANOVA revealed that the factors AgNP dose, exposure time, and species
495 significantly affect AFB₁ and AFB₂ production by both species. In addition, AFG₁ and
496 AFG₂ levels in *A. parasiticus* cultures were also significantly influenced by exposure
497 time and AgNP dose. Two-way interactions between species and both exposure time
498 and AgNP dose were significant for AFB₁ and AFB₂. As shown in Table 4 the Duncan's
499 test arranged the seven doses into five homogenous groups with some overlapping
500 (doses of 30, 5 and 2 µg/mL were included in two homogenous groups), and the
501 exposure time into three homogenous groups (2, 4 and 20–30 h) with regard to its
502 influence on AFB₁ and AFB₂. ANOVA also found significant effects of exposure time
503 and dose on AFG₁ and AFG₂ levels in *A. parasiticus* cultures. Duncan's grouping for
504 both factors agreed quite well with the previously cited AF groups (Table 4). AF

505 concentration was positively correlated with GR and negatively correlated with lag
506 phase in *A. flavus* and *A. parasiticus* cultures. Low or undetected AF concentrations
507 correspond to long lag phases and low/null growth.

508 Fig. 8 shows the mean OTA levels from ochratoxigenic species in MBM
509 cultures. ANOVA found that all single factors significantly influence OTA production.
510 Two interactions (species × AgNP dose and species × exposure time) were also
511 significant ($p < 0.01$). Three homogenous groups were arranged by Duncan's test for
512 AgNP doses (controls, 2–5 µg/L, and the remaining doses) (Table 4). Regarding OTA
513 production, the studied species were placed in the three homogeneous non-
514 overlapping groups (Table 4). For each species, OTA level was positively correlated
515 with GR and negatively correlated with lag phase duration, as indicated for AF. MBM
516 cultures from controls or treatments leading to short lag periods (rapid germination) and
517 high GR were quickly colonized by fungi and mycotoxin levels were significantly higher
518 than levels found in cultures showing long lag phases and low GR. In these last cases,
519 most colonies did not spread over the total culture medium surface or this fact
520 happened in the last days of the incubation period.

521 Based on the results of our study, the mycotoxin levels found in MBM cultures
522 inoculated with treated spores (different AgNP doses and exposure times) are strongly
523 related to the colony size. Therefore, the partial or total inhibition of mycotoxin
524 production per plate is a direct consequence of the AgNP effect on fungal growth.
525 Some researchers have reported that inhibition of AFB₁ production in liquid cultures of
526 *A. flavus* supplemented with 50, 100 and 150 ppm of AgNPs ranged 48.2–61.8%,
527 46.1–82.2% and 100%, respectively (Al-Othman et al., 2014). Mousavi and Pourtalebi
528 (2015) also showed significant inhibition of AFB₁ biosynthesis at AgNP doses of 90
529 ppm. Recently, a significant impact of AgNPs on omt-A gene expression (involved in
530 AF biosynthesis) in *Aspergillus flavus* (ATCC 28542) has been described (Deabes,
531 Khalil, Attallah, El-Desouky, & Naguib, 2018). Thus, the set of results suggests that the
532 effect of AgNPs in controlling the production of mycotoxins by toxigenic fungi could be

533 related to the control of the growth of the fungus and alterations in the expression of
534 genes involved in the biosynthesis of mycotoxins. The set of available data, although
535 very limited (Horky, Skalickova, Baholet, & Skladanka, 2018; Deabes et al., 2018), and
536 the data from our study suggest that three main strategies could be considered in
537 relation of the usefulness of AgNPs in food technology: mold inhibition, inhibition of
538 gene expression and mycotoxin adsorption. Further studies will be necessary to
539 confirm this hypothesis.

540 In summary, the results from our study permit to conclude that AgNP treatments
541 are very effective in controlling the growth of aflatoxigenic and ochratoxigenic fungi and
542 AF and OTA production at very low doses and short exposure periods. The most
543 susceptible fungi to AgNPs were species from section *Circumdati* (*A. steynii*, *A.*
544 *ochraceus* and *A. westerdijkiae*) followed by *P. verrucosum* and species from section
545 *Flavi* (*A. flavus* and *A. parasiticus*). Therefore, AgNPs could be used in solutions for
546 cleaning chambers, silos or as active ingredients of paint, films, packaging or other
547 coating useful in the agri-food sector and they may be a promising strategy in the
548 management of these fungi and mycotoxins in food.

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554 071242), respectively.

555 **References**

556 Abd-Elsalam, K. A., Hashim, A. F., Alghuthaymi, M. A., & Said-Galiev, E. (2017).
557 Nanobiotechnological strategies for toxigenic fungi and mycotoxin control. In A.
558 M. Grumezescu (Ed.). *Food Preservation, Vol. 6.* (pp 337–364). Elsevier Inc.

559 Agnihotri, S., Mukherji, S., & Mukherji, S. (2014). Size-controlled silver nanoparticles
560 synthesized over the range 5–100 nm using the same protocol and their
561 antibacterial efficacy. *RSC Advances*, 4, 3974–3983.

562 Ahmad, A., Wei, Y., Syed, F., Tahir, K., Rehman, A. U., Khan, A., et al. (2017). The
563 effects of bacteria-nanoparticles interface on the antibacterial activity of green
564 synthesized silver nanoparticles. *Microbial Pathogenesis*, 102, 133–142.

565 Al-Othman, M. R., Abd El-aziz, A. R. M., Mahmoud, M. A., Eifan. S. A., El-shikh, M. S.,
566 & Majrashi, M. (2014). Application of silver nanoparticles as antifungal and
567 antiaflatoxin B1 produced by *Aspergillus flavus*. *Digest Journal of Nanomaterials*
568 *and Biostructures*, 9, 151–157.

569 Baker, S., Volova, T., Prudnikova, S. V., Satish, S., & Prasad M. N. N. (2017).
570 Nanoagroparticles emerging trends and future prospect in modern agriculture
571 system. *Environmental Toxicology and Pharmacology*, 53, 10–17.

572 Battilani, P., Rossi, V., Giorni, P., Pietri, A., Gualla, A., van der Fels-Klerx, H. J., et al.
573 (2012). Scientific Report submitted to EFSA. Modelling, predicting and mapping
574 the emergence of aflatoxins in cereals in the EU due to climate change. Question
575 No EFSA-Q-2009-00812.

576 Battilani, P. (2016). Recent advances in modeling the risk of mycotoxin contamination
577 in crops Review. *Current Opinion in Food Science*, 11, 10–15.

578 Bocate, K. P., Reis, G. F., de Souza, P. C., Oliveira Junior, A. G., Durán, N., Nakazato,
579 G., et al. (2019). Antifungal activity of silver nanoparticles and simvastatin against
580 toxigenic species of *Aspergillus*. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, 291,
581 79–86.

582 Bui-Klimke, T. R., & Wu, F. (2015). Ochratoxin A and human health risk: A review of
583 the evidence. *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition*, 55, 1860–1869.

584 Covarelli, L., Beccari, G., Marini, A., & Tosi, L. (2012). A review on the occurrence and
585 control of ochratoxigenic fungal species and ochratoxin A in dehydrated grapes,

586 nonfortified dessert wines and dried vine fruit in the Mediterranean area. *Food*
587 *Control*, 26, 347–356.

588 da Silva-Ferreira, V., ConzFerreira, M. E., Lima, L. M. T. R., Frases, S., de Souza, W.,
589 & Sant'Anna, C. (2017). Green production of microalgae-based silver chloride
590 nanoparticles with antimicrobial activity against pathogenic bacteria. *Enzyme and*
591 *Microbial Technology*, 97, 114–121.

592 Deabes, M. M., Khalil, W. K. B., Attallah, A. G., El-Desouky, T. A., & Naguib, Kh. M.
593 (2018). Impact of silver nanoparticles on gene expression in *Aspergillus flavus*
594 producer aflatoxin B1. *Open Access Macedonian Journal of Medical Sciences*, 6,
595 600–605. <https://doi.org/10.3889/oamjms.2018.117>.

596 Denhavi, A. S., Aroujalian, A., Raisi, A., & Fazel. S. (2013). Preparation and
597 characterization of polyethylene-silver nanocomposite films with antibacterial
598 activity. *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, 127, 1180–1190.

599 Duarte, S. C., Pena, A., & Lino, C. M. (2010). A review on ochratoxin A occurrence and
600 effects of processing of cereal and cereal derived food products. *Food*
601 *Microbiology*, 27,187–198.

602 Egger, S., Lehmann, R. P., Height, M. J., Loessner, M. J., & Schuppler, M. 2009.
603 Antimicrobial properties of a novel silver-silica nanocomposite material. *Applied*
604 *and Environmental Microbiology*, 75, 2973–2976.

605 European Commission. (2006). Commission Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006 of 19
606 December 2006 setting maximum levels for certain contaminants in foodstuffs.
607 *Official Journal of the European Union*, L 364, 5–24.
608 <http://extwprlegs1.fao.org/docs/pdf/eur68134.pdf>.

609 European Union, 2017. The Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed (RASFF), Reports
610 and publications 2002–2016.
611 https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/rasff/reports_publications_en.

612 Gil-Serna, J., García-Díaz, M., González-Jaén, M. T., Vázquez, C., & Patiño, B. (2018).
613 Description of an orthologous cluster of ochratoxin A biosynthetic genes in

614 *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium* species. A comparative analysis. *International Journal*
615 *of Food Microbiology*, 269,107–119.

616 Giorni, P., Bertuzzi, T., & Battilani, P. (2016). Aflatoxin in maize, a multifaceted answer
617 of *Aspergillus flavus* governed by weather, host-plant and competitor fungi.
618 *Journal of Cereal Science*, 70, 256–262.

619 Gómez, J. V., Tarazona, A., Mateo-Castro, R., Gimeno-Adelantado, J. V., Jiménez, M.,
620 & Mateo, E. M. (2018). Selected plant essential oils and their main active
621 components, a promising approach to inhibit aflatoxigenic fungi and aflatoxin
622 production in food. *Food Additives and Contaminants: Part A*, 35, 1581–1595.

623 Hofmann-Antenbrink, M., Grainger, D. W., & Hofmann, H. (2015). Nanoparticles in
624 medicine: Current challenges facing inorganic nanoparticle toxicity assessments
625 and standardizations. *Nanomedicine: Nanotechnology, Biology and Medicine*, 11,
626 1689–1694.

627 Horky, P., Skalickova, S., Baholet, D., & Skladanka, J. (2018). Nanoparticles as a
628 solution for eliminating the risk of mycotoxins. *Nanomaterials*, 8, 727. doi:
629 10.3390/nano8090727.

630 Huy, T. Q., Hien Thanh, N. T., Thuy, N. T., Chung, P. V., Hung, P. N., Le, A. T., et al.
631 (2017). Cytotoxicity and antiviral activity of electrochemical – synthesized silver
632 nanoparticles against poliovirus. *Journal of Virological Methods*, 241, 52–57.

633 IARC (1993). Some naturally occurring substances: food items and constituents,
634 heterocyclic aromatic amines and mycotoxins, pp. 489–521. IARC monographs
635 on the evaluation of carcinogenic risks to humans, vol. 56. International Agency
636 for Research on Cancer, Lyon, France.

637 Iqbal, S. Z., Jinap, S., Pirouz, A. A., & Faizal, A. R. A. (2015). Aflatoxin M1 in milk and
638 dairy products, occurrence and recent challenges: A review. *Trends in Food*
639 *Science and Technology*, 46, 110–119.

640 Ismaiel, A. A., & Tharwat, N. A. (2014). Antifungal activity of silver ion on ultrastructure
641 and production of aflatoxin B1 and patulin by two mycotoxigenic strains,

642 *Aspergillus flavus* OC1 and *Penicillium vulpinum* CM. *Journal de Mycologie*
643 *Médicale*, 24, 193–204.

644 James, A., & Zikankuba, V. L. (2018). Mycotoxins contamination in maize alarms food
645 safety in sub-Saharan Africa. *Food Control*, 90, 372–381.

646 Jogee, P. S., Ingle, A. P., & Mahendra, R. (2017). Isolation and identification of
647 toxigenic fungi from infected peanuts and efficacy of silver nanoparticles against
648 them. *Food Control*, 71, 143–151.

649 Kim, S. W., Jung, J. H., Lamsal, K., Kim, Y. S., Min, J. S., & Lee, Y. S. (2012).
650 Antifungal effects of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) against various plant
651 pathogenic fungi. *Mycobiology*, 40, 53–58.

652 Klingelhöfer, D., Zhu, Y., Braun M., Brüggmann, D., & Groneberg, D. A. (2018).
653 Aflatoxin – Publication analysis of a global health threat. *Food Control*, 89, 280–
654 290.

655 Kotzybik, K., Gräf, V., Kugler, L., Stoll, D. A., Greiner, R., Geisen, R., et al., (2016).
656 Influence of different nanomaterials on growth and mycotoxin production of
657 *Penicillium verrucosum*. *PLOS One*, 11(3), e0150855.
658 doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0150855.

659 Kumar, P., Mahato, D. P., Kamle, M., Mohanta, T. K., & Kang, S. G. (2017). Aflatoxins:
660 a global concern for food safety, human health and their management. *Frontiers*
661 *in Microbiology*, 17, January 2017. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2016.02170>.

662 Kvítek, L., Panáček, A. Soukupová, J., Kolař, M., Večeřová, R., Pucek, R., et al.
663 (2008). Effect of surfactants and polymers on stability and antibacterial activity of
664 silver nanoparticles (NPs). *Journal of Physical Chemistry C*, 112, 5825–5834.

665 Li, H. J., Zhang, A. Q., Hu, Y., Sui, L., Qian, D. J., & Chen, M. (2012). Large scale
666 synthesis and self-organization of silver nanoparticles with Tween 80 as a
667 reductant and stabilizer. *Nanoscale Research Letters*, 7, 612–625.

668 Lund, F., & Frisvad, J. C. (2003). *Penicillium verrucosum* in wheat and barley indicates
669 presence of ochratoxin A. *Journal of Applied Microbiology*, 95, 1117–1123.

670 Ma, Z., & Michailides, T. (2005). Advances in understanding molecular mechanisms of
671 fungicide resistance and molecular detection of resistant genotypes in
672 phytopathogenic fungi. *Crop Protection*, 24, 853–863.

673 Marroquín-Cardona, A. G., Johnson, N. M., Phillips, T. D., & Hayes, A. W. (2015).
674 Mycotoxins in a changing global environment – A review. *Food and Chemical*
675 *Toxicology*, 69, 220–230.

676 Mateo, R., Medina, A., Mateo, F., Mateo, E. M., & Jiménez, M. (2007). An overview of
677 ochratoxin A in beer and wine. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, 119,
678 79–83.

679 Mateo, E. M., Valle-Algarra, F. M., Mateo-Castro, R., & Jiménez, M. (2011a). Impact of
680 non-selective fungicides on the growth and production of ochratoxin A by
681 *Aspergillus ochraceus* and *A. carbonarius* in barley-based medium. *Food*
682 *Additives and Contaminants: Part A*, 28, 86–97.

683 Mateo, E. M., Gil-Serna, J., Patiño, B., & Jiménez, M. (2011b). Aflatoxins and
684 ochratoxin A in stored barley grain in Spain and impact of PCR-based strategies
685 to assess the occurrence of aflatoxigenic and ochratoxigenic *Aspergillus* spp.
686 *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, 149, 118–126.

687 Mateo, E. M., Valle-Algarra, F. M., Jiménez, M., & Magan, N. (2013). Impact of three
688 sterol-biosynthesis inhibitors on growth of *Fusarium langsethiae* and on T-2 and
689 HT-2 toxin production in oat grain under different ecological conditions. *Food*
690 *Control*, 34, 521–529.

691 Mateo, E. M., Gómez, J. V., Gimeno-Adelantado, J. V., Romera, D. Mateo-Castro, R.,
692 & Jiménez, M. (2017a). Assessment of azole fungicides as a tool to control
693 growth of *Aspergillus flavus* and aflatoxin B1 and B2 production in maize. *Food*
694 *Additives and Contaminants: Part A*, 34, 1039–1051.

695 Mateo, E. M., Gómez, J. V., Domínguez, I., Gimeno-Adelantado, J. V., Mateo-Castro,
696 R., Gavara, R., et al. (2017b). Impact of bioactive packaging systems based on

697 EVOH films and essential oils in the control of aflatoxigenic fungi and aflatoxin
698 production in maize. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, 254, 36–46.

699 Medina, A., Mateo, R., López-Ocaña, L., Valle-Algarra, F. M., & Jiménez, M. (2005).
700 Study of Spanish grape mycobiota and ochratoxin A production by isolates of
701 *Aspergillus tubingensis* and other members of *Aspergillus* section *Nigri*. *Applied*
702 *and Environmental Microbiology*, 71, 4696–4702.

703 Medina, A., Jiménez, M., Mateo, R., & Magan, N. (2007). Natamycin efficacy for control
704 of growth and ochratoxin production by *Aspergillus carbonarius* isolates under
705 different environmental regimes. *Journal of Applied Microbiology*, 103, 2234–
706 2239.

707 Mousavi, S. A. A. & Pourtalebi, S. (2015). Inhibitory effects of silver nanoparticles on
708 growth and aflatoxin B1 production by *Aspergillus parasiticus*. *Iranian Journal of*
709 *Medical Sciences*, 40, 501–506.

710 Nguyen, N., Long, V., Joly, C., & Dantigny, P. (2016). Active packaging with antifungal
711 activities. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, 220, 73–90.

712 Paramelle, D., Sadovoy, A., Gorelik, S., Free, P., Hobley, J. & Fernig, D. G. (2014). A
713 rapid method to estimate the concentration of citrate capped silver nanoparticles
714 from UV-visible light spectra. *Analyst*, 139, 4855–4861.

715 Qian, Y., Yu, H., He, D., Yang, H., Wang, W., Wan, X., et al. (2013). Biosynthesis of
716 silver nanoparticles by the endophytic fungus *Epicoccum nigrum* and their activity
717 against pathogenic fungi. *Bioprocess and Biosystems Engineering*, 36, 1613–
718 1619.

719 Rai, P. K., Kumar, V., Lee, S., Raza, N., Kim, K-H., Ok, Y. S., et al. (2018). Review
720 article. Nanoparticle-plant interaction: Implications in energy, environment, and
721 agriculture. *Environment International*, 119, 1–19.

722 Romera, D., Mateo, E. M., Mateo-Castro, R., Gómez, J. V., Gimeno-Adelantado, J.V.,
723 & Jiménez, M. (2018). Determination of multiple mycotoxins in feedstuffs by

724 combined use of UPLC–MS/MS and UPLC–QTOF–MS. *Food Chemistry*, 267,
725 140-148.

726 Taniwaki, M. H., Pitt J. I., & Magan, N. (2018). *Aspergillus* species and mycotoxins:
727 occurrence and importance in major food commodities. *Current Opinion in Food*
728 *Science*, 23, 38-43.

729 Tarazona, A., Gómez, J. V., Gavara, R., Mateo-Castro, R., Gimeno-Adelantado, J. V.,
730 Jiménez, M., et al. (2018). Risk management of ochratoxigenic fungi and
731 ochratoxin A in maize grains by bioactive EVOH films containing individual
732 components of some essential oils. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*,
733 269, 107–119.

734 Torres, A. M., Barros, G. G., Palacios, S. A., Chulze, S. N., & Battilani, P. (2014).
735 Review on pre- and post-harvest management of peanuts to minimize *aflatoxin*
736 contamination. *Food Research International*, 62, 11–19.

737 Yassin, M. A., El-Samawaty, A. E-R., Dawoud, T. M., Abd-Elkader, O. H., Al Maary, K.
738 S., et al. (2017). Characterization and anti-*Aspergillus flavus* impact of
739 nanoparticles synthesized by *Penicillium citrinum*. *Saudi Journal of Biological*
740 *Sciences*, 24, 1243–1248.

741 **Figure captions**

742

743 Fig. 1. Size distribution of AgNPs obtained by SP-ICP-MS.

744 Fig. 2. (a) Micrograph of AgNPs obtained by TEM, (b) Size distribution of AgNPs
745 obtained by TEM.

746 Fig. 3. UV-Vis spectra of AgNP suspension in a 0.005% Tween 80 from 300 to 800 nm
747 at 0 (initial), 2, 4, 20 and 30 hours.

748 Fig. 4. Spore viability of aflatoxigenic and ochratoxigenic species on Maize Based
749 Medium after different treatments with AgNPs. Error bars represent standard
750 deviations.

751 Fig. 5. Lag period (days) in colonies of aflatoxigenic and ochratoxigenic species on
752 Maize Based Medium after different treatments with AgNPs. Standard deviations
753 ranged between 0 and 5 hours. Error bars were not included because of poor visibility.

754 Fig. 6. Growth rates (GR, mm/day) of aflatoxigenic and ochratoxigenic species on
755 Maize Based Medium after different treatments with AgNPs. Error bars represent
756 standard deviations.

757 Fig. 7. Aflatoxin production ($\mu\text{g/g}$) by *A. flavus* and *A. parasiticus* in Maize Based
758 Medium after different treatments with AgNPs. Incubation time 10 days. Incubation
759 temperature 37 °C. Error bars represent standard deviations.

760 Fig. 8. Ochratoxin A production ($\mu\text{g/g}$) by *A. carbonarius*, *A. niger*, *A. ochraceus*, *A.*
761 *steynii*, *A. westerdijkiae* and *P. verrucosum* in Maize Based Medium after different
762 treatments with AgNPs. Incubation time 10 days. Incubation temperature 28 °C except
763 in *P. verrucosum* cultures (20 °C). Error bars represent standard deviations.

764

Table 1

ED₅₀^a, ED₉₀^b and ED₁₀₀^c of AgNPs (µg/mL spore suspension) against spores of aflatoxigenic and ochratoxigenic species at different exposure times.

Fungal species	Exposure time AgNPs–fungal spores											
	2 h			4 h			20 h			30 h		
	ED ₅₀	ED ₉₀	ED ₁₀₀	ED ₅₀	ED ₉₀	ED ₁₀₀	ED ₅₀	ED ₉₀	ED ₁₀₀	ED ₅₀	ED ₉₀	ED ₁₀₀
<i>A. flavus</i>	>45	>45	>45	34.0	>45	>45	7.3	17.0	30.0	2.0	11.7	15.0
<i>A. parasiticus</i>	>45	>45	>45	37.5	>45	>45	2.5	17.7	45.0	1.8	14.5	30.0
<i>A. carbonarius</i>	>45	>45	>45	30.6	42.2	45.0	1.9	9.1	10.0	1.4	4.2	10.0
<i>A. niger</i>	>45	>45	>45	25.4	>45	>45	2.8	6.8	15.0	1.1	2.0	15.0
<i>A. ochraceus</i>	>45	>45	>45	12.9	>45	>45	1.6	7.5	15.0	1.8	4.5	5.0
<i>A. steynii</i>	>45	>45	>45	16.9	>45	>45	1.5	4.9	15.0	1.0	1.8	5.0
<i>A. westerdijkiae</i>	>45	>45	>45	23.5	>45	>45	1.6	7.6	15.0	1.3	3.1	5.0
<i>P. verrucosum</i>	26.7	41.5	45.0	25.6	41.3	45.0	4.2	12.1	15.0	3.2	9.2	15.0

^a, ^b, and ^c: AgNP dose required to reduce the number of viable spores by 50%, 90%, and 100% compared to untreated controls under identical conditions.

Table 2

Arrangement of homogeneous groups within AgNP doses, aflatoxigenic and ochratoxigenic species, and exposure times, with regard to the effects of AgNPs on spore viability, lag phase and growth rate in maize-based medium cultures according to Duncan's multiple comparison procedure.

Factor	Level	Spore viability			Lag phase			Growth rate			
		High	→	Low	Low	→	High	High	→	Low	
AgNP dose (µg/mL)	0	•			•			•			
	2		•			•		•			
	5			•			•		•		
	10				•			•		•	
	15					•			•	•	
	30							•		•	•
	45								•		•
Fungal species	<i>A. flavus</i>	•			•				•		
	<i>A. parasiticus</i>	•	•		•			•	•		
	<i>A. carbonarius</i>		•	•		•		•			
	<i>A. niger</i>		•	•		•			•		
	<i>A. ochraceus</i>			•		•				•	
	<i>A. steynii</i>					•				•	
	<i>A. westerdijkiae</i>			•		•				•	
	<i>P. verrucosum</i>	•	•	•		•					•
Exposure time (h)	2	•			•			•			
	4		•		•				•		
	20			•		•				•	
	30			•			•			•	

Within each column, the levels containing a black circle form a group of means within which there are no statistically significant differences ($\alpha = 0.05$).

Table 3

Effective doses (ED₅₀^a, ED₉₀^b and ED₁₀₀^c) of AgNPs (µg/ml) in treatments of aflatoxigenic and ochratoxigenic species to reduce/inhibit further colonial development in maize-based medium free of AgNPs.

Fungal species	Exposure time AgNPs-fungal spores (h)											
	2			4			20			30		
	ED ₅₀	ED ₉₀	ED ₁₀₀	ED ₅₀	ED ₉₀	ED ₁₀₀	ED ₅₀	ED ₉₀	ED ₁₀₀	ED ₅₀	ED ₉₀	ED ₁₀₀
<i>A. flavus</i>	>45	>45	>45	>45	>45	>45	21.7	28.4	30.0	12.0	14.4	15.0
<i>A. parasiticus</i>	>45	>45	>45	>45	>45	>45	36.5	43.3	45.0	20.7	28.1	30.0
<i>A. carbonarius</i>	>45	>45	>45	33	42.6	45	7.2	9.5	10.0	7.1	9.4	10.0
<i>A. niger</i>	>45	>45	>45	>45	>45	>45	12.2	14.4	15.0	12.0	14.4	15.0
<i>A. ochraceus</i>	>45	>45	>45	>45	>45	>45	10.4	14.3	15.0	3.5	4.7	5.0
<i>A. steynii</i>	>45	>45	>45	>45	>45	>45	11.3	14.4	15.0	2.9	4.6	5.0
<i>A. westerdijkiae</i>	>45	>45	>45	>45	>45	>45	11.8	14.3	15.0	3.4	4.7	5.0
<i>P. verrucosum</i>	36.3	43.3	45.0	34.0	42.8	45.0	12.4	14.5	15.0	12.0	14.4	15.0

^a, ^b and ^c: AgNP dose required to reduce colony radial growth rate by 50%, 90% and 100% compared to untreated control under identical conditions

Table 4

Arrangement of homogeneous groups within AgNP doses, exposure times and fungal species with regard to their effects on mycotoxin accumulation in maize-based medium cultures by various species of *Fusarium* according to Duncan's multiple comparison test.

Factor		Mycotoxin														
		AFB ₁			AFB ₂			AFG ₁			AFG ₂			OTA		
		High	→	Low	High	→	Low									
AgNP dose (µg/ml)	0	•			•			•			•			•		
	2	•	•		•	•		•	•		•	•			•	
	5		•	•		•	•		•	•		•	•		•	•
	10			•			•		•			•				•
	15				•			•			•			•		•
	30			•	•		•	•		•	•		•	•		•
	45				•			•			•			•		•
Exposure time (h)	2	•			•			•			•			•		
	4		•			•			•			•			•	
	20			•			•			•			•		•	
	30			•			•			•			•		•	
Fungal	<i>A. flavus</i>		•			•										
	<i>A. parasiticus</i>	•				•										
	<i>A. carbonarius</i>														•	
	<i>A. niger</i>															•
	<i>A. ochraceus</i>													•		
	<i>A. steynii</i>													•		
	<i>A. westerdijkiae</i>														•	
	<i>P. verrucosum</i>															•

Within each column, the levels containing a black circle form a group of means within which there are no statistically significant differences ($\alpha = 0.05$). Black circles in the same row indicate overlapping.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

Figure 6

